

ENOL CONTENT OF 2-FORMYL KETONES (HYDROXYMETHYLENE KETONES). PART II

BY MISHRI MAL BOKADIA AND S. S. DESHPANDE

Enol contents of some more hydroxymethylene ketones have been estimated by the methods of K. H. Meyer and Hibber and a difference between the two results, as reported previously, has again been observed. Enols have also been estimated by titration against *N*/5 caustic soda solution at -10° and the values obtained are found to be in agreement with those obtained by Meyer's method.

In Part I (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 455) the enol contents of five hydroxymethylene ketones were reported and it was shown that the enol contents determined by K. H. Meyer's method (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2718) were generally higher than those obtained by Hibber's copper acetate method (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 902). We have extended the work and have determined enol contents of (1) hydroxymethylene menthone, (2) hydroxymethylene cyclopentanone, (3) hydroxymethylene bromoethyl acetate and hydroxymethylene bromoacetone by both these methods. We have confirmed our previous observation that the values for enol content obtained by K. H. Meyer's method are in each case higher than those obtained by Hibber's method. These results are shown in Table I.

In regard to the stages constituting K. H. Meyer's bromine process, evidence about the formation of dibromo addition product of enol and of the formation of the corresponding bromoketone by loss of hydrobromic acid from it, which constitute the first and the second stage respectively of the process, was shown in a paper by one of us (S. S. D.) (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 43). The third stage in the process is the reduction of bromoketone to the parent ketone by acidified potassium iodide with the liberation of two atoms of iodine per molecule of the enol. This stage has now been examined by us. By means of acidified potassium iodide we reduced some bromo- β -ketonic esters, two bromohydroxymethylene ketones, and two simple α -bromoketones. The iodine liberated was found in each case to be about equal to the calculated value, namely two atoms of iodine per molecule of the bromo compound. These results are shown in Table II of the experimental part. Thus, the mechanism postulated by K. H. Meyer in his process of estimating enol has been critically examined and verified.

That the parent hydroxymethylene ketone was actually formed by the action of acidified potassium iodide on the bromoketone, produced at an intermediate stage in the Meyer's process, was demonstrated by starting with hydroxymethylene cyclopentanone, which is a solid. On treatment with bromine, followed by addition of acidified potassium iodide, iodine was liberated which was titrated against sodium thiosulphate. On extracting with ether the liquid left after titration and on removal of its solvent, the residue was identified to be hydroxymethylene cyclopentanone.

The discrepancy about the results of enol content obtained by the methods of Meyer and Hibber, however, could not be explained.

A method for estimating enol in a keto-enol equilibrium mixture has been suggested by Seidel *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 650) who titrated an absolute alcoholic solution of the mixture at -10° with *N*/5 caustic soda solution. The authors have shown that under these conditions the values of enol obtained are in close agreement with those obtained by K. H. Meyer's method. We used the titration method in the case of some hydroxymethylene ketones and found that here too there is a good agreement between the results obtained by the titration method and Meyer's method. These results are shown in Table III.

EXPERIMENTAL

The estimations of the enol contents by Meyer's method and Hibber's method were carried out exactly in the same way as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The results obtained are given below.

TABLE I

	Hydroxymethylene ketones.	Percentage of enol by		Reference
		Meyer's method.	Hibber's method.	
1	Hydroxymethylene cyclopentanone	99.3%	47.87%	Wallach <i>et al.</i> , <i>Annalen</i> , 1903, 320, 114.
2	Hydroxymethylene menthone	74.0	20.0	Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair, <i>Annalen</i> , 1894, 281, 394.
3	Hydroxymethylene bromoacetone	55.58	15.32	Mahala & Deshapande (unpublished work)
4	Hydroxymethylene bromoethyl acetate	78.6	...	Gupta & Deshapande (unpublished work)

Reduction of Bromoketonic Systems.—Weighed amounts of bromoketones were dissolved in absolute alcohol and treated with acidified potassium iodide and slightly warmed. The iodine liberated was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The results obtained are given in Table II.

TABLE II

	Bromo compounds.				Amount of iodine liberated by 1 gram mol. of bromoketone.	Mols. of iodine
1.	α -Bromoethyl acetoacetate	...	...	...	252.5 g.	0.99 mol.
2.	γ -Bromoethyl acetoacetate	...	...	...	257.4	1.01
3.	$\alpha\alpha$ -Dibromoethyl acetoacetate	...	..	...	499.2	1.96
4.	Hydroxymethylene bromoacetone	...	...	...	249.5	0.98
5.	Hydroxymethylene bromoacetophenone	...	...	...	253.0	0.99
6.	2-Bromoacetone	...	...	...	254.1	1.00
7.	α -Bromoacetophenone	...	...	...	254.0	1.00

Recovery of the Parent Compound from the Reduction Product.—To absolute alcoholic solution of hydroxymethylene cyclopentanone alcoholic solution of bromine was

added in slight excess at room temperature until a faint red colour persisted. On adding a strong aqueous solution of potassium iodide, followed by 2 c.c. of dilute sulphuric acid, iodine was liberated which was removed by adding aqueous sodium thiosulphate. On extracting the solution with ether and on removal of the solvent, a solid residue was left which on purification by crystallisation melted at 73°, and was thus identified as hydroxymethylene cyclopentanone.

Enol Content by Caustic Soda Titration Method.—Dittmer (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 650) carried out the titrations of keto-enol mixtures at room temperature. Several experiments were performed by us at various temperatures and the following method was found to give reliable results.

A weighed amount of the substance was dissolved in absolute alcohol and cooled to -10°. This was titrated against *N/5* aqueous caustic soda solution using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The results obtained are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Hydroxymethylene ketones.	Percentage of enol by		
	NaOH method.	Meyer's method.	Hibber's method
1. Hydroxymethylene methylethyl ketone ...	96.0%	96.0%	64.1%
2. " diethyl ketone ...	98.97	97.0	35.5
3. " desoxybenzoin ...	90.0	90.2	89.7
4. " cyclohexanone ...	73	72.5	74.5
5. " cyclopentanone ...	99.0	99.3	47.87
6. " menthone ...	74.0	74.5	20.0

* The value of the enol content reported in Part I was 57%. The compound then prepared was liquid and was purified by distillation. We prepared the compound now in winter and obtained it as a solid (m.p. 40°). The enol estimation was done with the solid compound this time.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

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